

MultiModX

Performance framework and multimodal evaluators for the assessment of air-rail networks

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Towards a multimodal transport system

- The role of rail in the multimodal air transport network
 - Direct substitution/competition/complementarity
 - Feeder/Distributor from hub
 - Increasing catchment area

Complex interaction driven by passengers!

Door to Door

Modelling multimodal networks

Need for an **evaluation framework and tools**

Modelling multimodal networks

- Need to quantify the impact of
 - Strategic aspects
 - Large disruptions multimodal management
 - Tactical aspects

MultiModX

Performance Assessment Support Framework and Tools

- Provides a **multimodal performance framework**.
- **Strategic evaluation of networks** → design, development and assessment of strategic aspects (schedules, policies).
- **Evaluation of replanned networks** (under disruptions) → multimode resilience
- **Tactical evaluation of networks** → evaluates the robustness of planned networks and tactical mechanisms

Multimodal Performance Framework

Multimodal Performance Framework

- Digital catalogue of indicators
- Passenger-centric
- Open (collaborative)

■ KPAs and example indicators

• Operational Efficiency

- Pax processing time
- Total journey time
- Buffers in itineraries
- Missed connections
- ...

• Interoperability

- Modal share
- Infrastructure connectivity
- ...

• Flexibility

- Diversity of destinations
- ...

• Cost-Efficiency

- Load factors
- ...

• Capacity

- Demand served
- Catchment area
- ...

• Environment

• Predictability

Strategic Evaluation of Networks

Strategic Evaluation of Networks

- Evaluate strategic aspects of schedules and timetable from a mobility (and multimodality) perspective

Strategic Evaluation of Networks

Multilayer modelling

- Regions with demand for pax archetypes
- Infrastructure nodes (stations, airports) with access/egress
- Services (temporal edges)
- Transitions (minimum connecting time, pax processing time)

Path finding algorithms

Demand distribution
(pax preferences)

Pax flows
disaggregation
(pax itineraries)

Strategic Evaluation of Networks

Functional view

1. Find potential and possible paths between regions
2. Path clustering and filtering
3. Demand distribution to clusters (logit model)
4. Assignment of passengers to individual services (disaggregation of passengers)

Strategic Evaluation of Networks

Capabilities

- Assesses mobility from a passenger-centric perspective

Strategic Evaluation of Networks

Capabilities

- Assesses mobility from a passenger-centric perspective
- Metrics at different levels: region, infrastructure, operator level

50 itineraries → 15 clusters →
4 Filtered clusters
[2 air, 1 multimodal 1 rail]
(13 itineraries)

Demand distribution
(pax preferences)

Pax flows
disaggregation
(pax itineraries)

Example of strategic evaluations

- Scenarios defined as combination of:
 - Intra-Spain mobility,
 - Policy packages

Policy Package	Individual policies definition
Reference (no particular policies)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Passenger rights and multimodality: No integrated tickets (buffers in multimodal MCTs)• Environmental regulations: N/A• Limitation of aviation: N/A
Multimodality enforced	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Passenger rights and multimodality: Fully integrated (respecting alliances)• Environmental regulations: CO₂ tax applied to emissions• Limitation of aviation: Short-haul flight ban if rail available between regions <= 2h30

Strategic Evaluator – Examples of results

Policy packages

Policy Package	Name	Description
PP00	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multimodal connections allowed
PP20	Multimodality enforced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrated ticketing CO2 tax for aviation Short-haul flight ban

Demand served between regions

PP00

Strategic Evaluator – Examples of results

Policy packages

Policy Package	Name	Description
PP00	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multimodal connections allowed
PP20	Multimodality enforced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrated ticketing CO2 tax for aviation Short-haul flight ban

Total mobility time

Total mobility time from
ES511 to NUTS3 regions for
PP00

Strategic Evaluator – Examples of results

Policy packages

Policy Package	Name	Description
PP00	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multimodal connections allowed
PP20	Multimodality enforced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrated ticketing CO2 tax for aviation Short-haul flight ban

- Regional airports gain relevance as part of multimodal journeys
- Some airports not affected by the flight ban become also more relevant connectivity nodes (LEPA, LEIB)

Infrastructure connectivity

Pax

Egress PP00

Strategic Evaluator – Examples of results

Policy packages

Policy Package	Name	Description
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Demand satisfied and mode usage

- 80.9% original demand satisfied
- 70% average load factor
 - Some links saturated
- Passengers mostly shifted to HSR in PP20

	PP00 – Baseline	PP20 – Enforced (flight-ban)
Rail	72.1%	74.1%
Air	26.3%	23.8%
Multimodal	1.6%	2.1%

Evaluation of replanned networks (under disruptions)

Evaluation of replanned networks (under disruptions)

Multinetwork support each other

- Scenarios with different type of disruptions evaluated
 - rail links and airport closures,
 - industrial actions, and
 - reduced capacity.
- Update network (delays, cancellation, additional services)
- Assess passengers impacted (delayed/stranded) and replanning alternatives for them.

Passengers impacted for Madrid-Barcelona rail link closure

Tactical Evaluation of Networks

Description

Tactical Multimodal Evaluator

- Simulates the operations as they unfold on the day of execution.
- Tracks vehicles (flights and trains) and passengers, providing passenger-centric metrics.
- Can model disturbances and the mechanisms to manage them.
- Can consider
 - planned network
 - replanned networks with updated operations (schedules/timetables).

Description

Mercury

- Agent-Based Model for air transport
- Extended to include rail and passenger connection processes

Tactical Evaluator – Example results

Evaluation of Mechanisms to support multimodality

- Airport pre-departure fast-track mechanism

Fast-track to process passengers arriving at airport at different levels of speed-up

Conclusions

Conclusions

- Multimodality evaluator framework and tools.
- A **common performance framework** of the impact of multimodality (and competition/replacement) and passenger experience.
- A **set of tools** for the evaluation of planned, replanned and realised multimodal networks.
- Enables the evaluation of: technical solutions, policies, infrastructure changes, etc.

Multimodal Performance Framework

Evaluators

[https://github.com/
UoW-ATM/MultiModX](https://github.com/UoW-ATM/MultiModX)

Conclusions

■ Strategic Multimodal Performance Evaluator

- Planned networks
 - Consider competition (e.g. international hub)
 - Consider pricing changes
 - Analysing capacity-demand imbalances, infrastructure changes, timetable adjustments, etc.
 - Flexible so new modes could be added (e.g. long-distance buses)
 -
- Replanned networks:
 - Evaluate how one network could supports the other in the even of disruptions
 - Evaluate impact of integrated ticketing on passengers alternatives
 - ...

■ Tactical Multimodal Performance Evaluator

- Provide richer view of mobility network behaviour
- Evaluate mechanism to support connectivity
- Evaluate robustness of planned networks
- ...

<https://multimodx.eu/>

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Thank you!

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